

The following scheme explains the complete derivatographic result of $[\text{Zn}(\text{OHC}_6\text{H}_4\text{COO})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$.

Thus the complete decomposition of $[\text{Zn}(\text{OHC}_6\text{H}_4\text{COO})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ involves six steps out of which four are endothermal and rest are exothermal.

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Cadmium Complexes with 3-ethyl Pyridine and 3 : 5-Lutidine

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As a part of investigation on nitrogen bonded complexes of d^{10} metals several complexes of zinc(II) and cadmium(II) have been reported¹⁻³ with substituted pyridines and quinolines. We have been studying the donor ability of the ethyl and dimethyl substituted pyridines towards some d^{10} metal ions.

Earlier⁴ zinc complexes of ethyl and dimethyl substituted pyridines have been described. It was thought worthwhile to extend the investigation to the case of Cd(II) ion. As a result this communication reports some cadmium complexes of the general formula $[\text{CdL}_2\text{X}_2]$, where L is 3-ethyl pyridine and 3 : 5-lutidine and X is Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , NO_3^- and $[\text{CdL}_4]\text{Y}_2$, where Y is ClO_4^- .

Experimental

Compounds were prepared in ethanol medium by reacting cadmium salts with the ligands in 1 : 2 ratio. There was an almost immediate formation of the compounds which were filtered, washed with ethanol, followed by ether and dried in *vacuo*. Metal and halogen or thiocyanate were estimated by standard methods. Conductance was measured in acetone medium using a Toshniwal conductance bridge. Infrared spectra were recorded on Nujol mulls using Unicam SP200 spectrophotometer. Analytical and conductance data are recorded in Table 1 and spectral data in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

Complexes reported in the present investigation have a general composition $[\text{CdL}_2\text{X}_2]$ except the perchlorate complex having the formula $[\text{CdL}_4]\text{Y}_2$. All the compounds are white crystalline solids, have low melting points and are fairly soluble in acetone in which medium they are non-electrolytes, Δ_M being of the order of 8-15 mhos cm^2 (Table 1). The perchlorate complex has a Δ_M value of 250 mhos cm^2 indicative of 1 : 2 electrolytic nature of the complexes.

Infrared spectra show that most of the absorption bands due to free ligand are modified in the respective complexes indicating bonding to the metal ion. Absorption bands attributable to $\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$ in case of thiocyanato complex recorded in Table 2 are indicative of terminal N-bonded thiocyanate group. This is in conformity with earlier work on thiocyanato⁵⁻⁸ complexes.

Nitrato complexes are non-electrolytes indicating the non-ionic nature of the nitrato group. The position of ν_2 and ν_1 (Table 2) and their separation $\Delta\nu$ of $\sim 115 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ suggest the nitrato group to be monodentate in the present complexes on the basis of earlier observations⁹⁻¹¹.

The perchlorate complex having the composition $[\text{CdL}_4]\text{Y}_2$ has a molar conductance value of 250 mhos in acetone indicating 1 : 2 electrolytic nature of the complex. A weak band is observed at 930 cm^{-1} in addition to a broad band at 1115 cm^{-1} in the present case which confirms the ionic nature of perchlorate group in agreement with 1 : 2 electrolytic nature of the complex and earlier observations¹²⁻¹³. Hence, all the complexes reported in

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS, MELTING POINT AND CONDUCTANCE DATA OF CADMIUM COMPLEXES

Compound	Colour and form	m.p. (°C)	Conductance (mhos, cm ²)	%Cadmium		%Halogen or Thiocyanate	
				Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
CdCl ₂ (3 : 5-lut) ₂	White Crystalline	>260	8	27.98	28.28	17.72	17.86
CdBr ₂ (3 : 5-lut) ₂	"	242	8.5	22.86	23.12	32.66	32.87
CdI ₂ (3 : 5-lut) ₂	"	235	11.4	19.14	19.37	43.62	43.78
Cd(NO ₃) ₂ (3 : 5-lut) ₂	"	180	13.2	24.68	24.96	—	—
Cd(NCS) ₂ (3 : 5-lut) ₂	"	195	15	25.22	25.40	25.84	26.22
[Cd(3 : 5-lut) ₄](ClO ₄) ₂	"	220	250	14.85	15.20	—	—
CdCl ₂ (3-Etpty) ₂	"	210	8.5	28.05	28.28	17.62	17.86
CdBr ₂ (3-Etpty) ₂	"	202	11	22.88	23.12	32.54	32.87
CdI ₂ (3-Etpty) ₂	"	195	11.5	19.15	19.37	43.28	43.78
Cd(NO ₃) ₂ (3-Etpty) ₂	"	182	10.2	24.71	24.96	—	—
Cd(NCS) ₂ (3-Etpty) ₂	"	198	10.8	25.21	25.40	25.95	26.22

3 : 5-lut=3,5-dimethyl pyridine, 3-Etpty=3-ethylpyridine.

TABLE 2—INFRARED SPECTRA OF NITRATO, THIOCYANATO AND PERCHLORATE COMPLEXES (cm⁻¹)

Compound	ν ₂ (B ₂) out of plane rocking	Assignment ν ₁		ν ₂ (A ₁) (N-O)	ν ₃ (ClO ₄)	NO ₂ ν ₂ (A ₁) Sym.	Stretch ν ₄ (B ₁) Asym.	ν(C≡N)
		ν(C-S)	(ClO ₄)					
Cd(NO ₃) ₂ (3 : 5-lut) ₂	785 m	—	—	1055 s	—	1235 s	1400 s	—
Cd(NO ₃) ₂ (3-Etpty) ₂	790 m	—	—	1060 s	—	1280 s	1400 s	—
Cd(NCS) ₂ (3 : 5-lut) ₂	—	820 s	—	—	—	—	—	2080 vs
Cd(NCS) ₂ (3-Etpty) ₂	—	815 s	—	—	—	—	—	2065 vs
[Cd(3 : 5-lut) ₄](ClO ₄) ₂	—	—	935 m	—	1115 br (1060-1140)	—	—	—

the present investigation are four coordinated, presumably having a tetrahedral environment around the metal ion.

It is concluded that 3-ethyl pyridine and 3 : 5-dimethyl pyridine are considered to have good donor ability. In case the substituents would have reduced these ligands to poor donors due to steric factors, six-coordinated complexes could have been synthesised easily (instead of the four coordinated obtained now), since in case of a poor donor, more number of ligand molecules will be required to satisfy the acceptor capacity of the metal ion.

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Mercury Using 5, 6-Dibromo, 2, 3, 4-Trihydroxy Acetophenone

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THE presence of traces of mercury in the environment has caused concern because of its cumulative toxic effects¹. The different techniques used for the determination of small amounts of mercury have been recently reviewed by Chilov². Although the